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NOTES ON THE BIOGRAPHY OF MAJRUH MUGHANI

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Abstract

This study examines the life and literary legacy of Muhammadali beg Majruh Mughani, a lesser-known yet noteworthy poet of 19th-century Azerbaijani literature. Biographical data about Majruh are limited and primarily derived from manuscript materials and several tazkiras (biographical anthologies). His Divan, preserved at the M. Fuzuli Institute of Manuscripts of the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences, possesses autobiographical characteristics, featuring poems written in Azerbaijani with Persian headings that reveal personal experiences and dedications. Archival evidence, including correspondence with contemporaries such as Seyid Azim Shirvani, Mirza Ismayil beg Gasir, and Mirza Bakhish Nadim, demonstrates his active engagement in the literary life of Mughan, Shirvan, and broader Azerbaijani cultural circles.

The rediscovery and analysis of Majruh's creative heritage contribute to restoring an overlooked poet's place in literary history and offer valuable insights into the cultural and intellectual dynamics of 19th-century Azerbaijani literature.

Keywords: Majruh Mughani; 19th-century Azerbaijani literature; Divan; classical poetry; tazkira; Azerbaijani manuscript heritage; Azerbaijani cultural history.

Muhammadali beg Majruh Mughani, one of the lesser-studied but noteworthy figures of 19th-century Azerbaijani literary life, has very limited information available in the sources. Knowledge about his life, creative environment, and period of activity is mainly derived from manuscript materials and a small number of biographical collections (tazkiras).

The manuscript of Majruh Mughani's "Divan" is preserved at the Institute of Manuscripts named after M. Fuzuli of the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences. Since the manuscript is not in perfect condition, it is unfortunately impossible to determine its exact date of writing or read some of the poems. However, based on the type of script and paper, the manuscript can be attributed to the first half of the 19th century. The manuscript is incomplete at the beginning and end, measures 18×21 cm, consists of 115 pages, and is written in the shikasta script. The poems are in the poet's native language, Azerbaijani, but each poem has a Persian heading that indicates its theme, the person it is dedicated to, or the event it commemorates. These headings clarify events in the poet's personal life and explain the reason for the poem's creation and to whom it is dedicated. Reading the headings shows that the poems form a sequential chain of events, suggesting that the divan has an autobiographical character.

The poet's use of the pen name "Majruh" (meaning "wounded" or "broken-hearted") reflects both the symbolic traditions of classical literature and his inner spiritual state. This pen name indicates his closeness to themes of both earthly love and divine affection.

Although Majruh Mughani was known in his time, he later became one of the "shadowed artists" in literary history. One main reason his name remained outside the attention of literary scholars for many years was the ideological selectivity of the Soviet era. Soviet literary criticism gave insufficient space to representatives of

classical religious-philosophical poetry that did not conform to certain ideological patterns. Consequently, Majruh's works were neither published nor systematically studied.

Available information indicates that the poet was born in 1823 in Mughan. His father was named Muhammadrza. After receiving madrasa education in Ardabil, the poet returned to his native Mughan and engaged in creative activity. The reliability of this information is supported by facts obtained by Enver Chingizoglu. While researching the history of the Afshar tribe, whose role was significant in the ethnogenesis, politics, and culture of the Azerbaijani people, Chingizoglu encountered references to Majruh Mughani in Persian-language sources in Iranian libraries. He writes in the introduction to his book *Afshars*:

"We began our first journey tracing the Afshars from the Islamic Republic of Iran. The aim was to visit places where Afshars live, to get acquainted with their way of life... We intended to collect historical documents about the role of Afshars over centuries by visiting archives, museums, and libraries in Iran." [2, 3]

Although direct access to sources that could further verify this information is no longer possible due to Enver Chingizoglu's passing, the inclusion of the couplet "Spring has come, and once again the passionate nightingale will sing" (*Yaz oldu, genə bülbüli-şeyda gələcəkdiür*) from the divan at the end of his note supports the reliability of these findings.

Among the tazkiras we consulted to study Majruh Mughani's biography, the poet's name is mentioned in only three of them. The first reliable source providing initial information about him is the tazkira "Danishmendani-Azerbaijan". In this work by Muhammadali Terbiyet, there is no detailed information about the poet's life, works, or poetry. The information ends in three sentences:

“There were debates and disputes between Seyid Azim Shirvani and him. Majruh Mughani, Mirze Ali Mecmer Devechili, and Mecnun Tabrizi are among the poets mentioned in ‘Hadiqetush-shuara’. They wrote poems in the Turkish language.” [5, 222]

The second source is the tazkiras of Sayid Azim Shirvani. In his writings, Seyid Azim quotes two poems by Muhammadali beg Majruh and includes his own qasida titled “*To Majruh Mughani*” in his divan.

According to the information given in Terbiyet’s tazkira, there were disputes between Shirvani and Majruh. Known for silencing some poets with his mastery of words, Shirvani considered himself an authority in the art of poetry.

At this point, Salman Mumtaz’s remarks about Seyid Azim Shirvani’s relationship with the poets of Mughan are highly valuable:

“When Nabati passed away, Hajı Seyid Azim was about 9–10 years old. As he grew up and gained fame as a poet, he entered into debates and arguments with several poets over various issues. One of the unfortunate poets who suffered from Hajı Seyid Azim’s unfounded accusations was Muhammadali beg, known by the pen name ‘Majruh’ from Mughan. Faced with Seyid Azim’s truthful and sharp words, he was forced into silence. In a sarcastic response to Majruh’s poem, Seyid Azim describes Mughan and its steppes in the following lines from the ‘*Nafi*’ section of his poem:

He, the poet Khaki-Majruh, has dared mock me in verse,

Weaving foolish couplets — vain, without sense or grace.

He deems himself a jeweler of words in his art,

Though his being casts shadows, not beams from the heart.

Where is that courage, Majruh, within your frail frame,

To tread with a lion’s step — to dare, to proclaim?

He’s preferred Mughan’s barren plain to Shirvan’s proud land —

Ah, he could not discern his poor fortune’s hand. [7, 414]

Another book in which the poet’s name appears is “Suxanverani-Azerbaijan”, written in Persian by Aziz Dowlatabadi, a South Azerbaijani scholar and literary historian. This work, one of the key sources on the history of Azerbaijani literature, is a tazkira-type compilation that gathers information about poets and writers from different regions of Azerbaijan from the 10th to the 20th centuries, along with examples of their works [3, 2]. In the section titled “*Poets Who Wrote in the Azerbaijani Language*”, Majruh Mughani is also listed among the mentioned authors.

Another source that refers to the poet is the article “The Turkish Language During the Qajar Era” by Iranian historian Parviz Zare Shahmeresi [9]. Discussing poets who wrote in Turkish during the Qajar period, Shahmeresi refers to the tazkira “*Behcetush-shuara*” by Mohammad Kazem Asrar Alishah, which describes 19th-century Turkish poets:

“The book was written between 1294–1298 AH and contains information about 86 Azerbaijani poets who wrote in Turkish. The author explains that he was

motivated to write the book by Persian speakers who mocked the idea that there were no Turkish poets in Azerbaijan. Excellent information about these poets is given in ‘*Behcetush-shuara*’. Among them we can mention Ilahi Ardabili (d. 1296 AH), Zikri Ardabili, Majruh Mughani, Nabati (d. 1262 AH), Abdul Rashid Afshar, and Heyran Khanum.”

Another important source is the four-volume tazkira “A Collection of Poems by Famous Poets of Azerbaijan”, compiled by Azerbaijani enlightener Huseyn Afandi Gayibov. In the manuscript kept at the Institute of Manuscripts under code M-133, on page 1004, a short note about Majruh Mughani appears:

“Mughani ... village resident, the son of Muhammadrza bəy from Shirvan, the poet Muhammadali beg known by the pen name ‘Majruh’, author of a mukhammas, musaddas, and mustazad poem...”

Gayibov included in full Majruh Mughani’s mukhammas beginning with the verse “*Yaz oldu, genə bülbülü-şeyda gələcəkdir...*” [69, 1004].

The same poem is also preserved in Mirza Fatali Akhundov’s personal archive, stored in the Institute of Manuscripts under storage number 60/2.[1]

Although the author’s name is noted in the notebook, no information is provided about the time or place of its writing.

Among the materials preserved in Salman Mumtaz’s archive at the Institute of Manuscripts, there are also letters and poetic correspondences between Muhammadali beg Majruh Mughani and the lyrical-satirical poet Mirza Ismayil beg Gasir.

Gasir maintained correspondence not only with his contemporaries from Lankaran but also with poets from Shamakhi, Baku, Karabakh, Nakhchivan, and Tabriz — including Majruh Mughani, Seyid Azim Shirvani, Shirvanshahi, Mirza Muhammad Katib Karabakhi, Abdulla beg Asi, Gafil Shirvani, Molla Abbas Mahzun, and others.

Gasir’s letters addressed to Majruh are preserved in folder **B-1546/8188** in the archives of the Institute of Manuscripts.

These materials, written on scattered sheets, consist of a total of 104 pages, most of them in Persian... Among the documents in the folder are a Turkish ghazal beginning with the line “You saw my beloved once again among the beloveds” (*Gördün yənə cananımlı canan arasında*) and a reply letter to Majruh written in Azerbaijani.”

In his poetic letter, Gasir complains about poverty and expresses that despite the distance, he feels extremely happy to be friends with Muhammadali beg. In one of his mukhammas poems, Gasir mentions that he received Majruh’s letter while in Shusha and immediately replied:

While I was in Shusha, your letter reached my hand,

said: “*As fate has brought yours — my reply too shall stand.*”

Expressing sincere friendship toward Muhammadali beg, Gasir emphasizes that the poet enjoys great respect among the people. To support Majruh, who lamented about his old age, Gasir writes:

My sighs of age cry out to the cruel skies above,

O tyrant fate, why stir once more the storm of age and love?

My soul grew faint with fear — my beloved turned away in rage.

In the final lines of this poetic letter, both poets criticize a mutual acquaintance — a mullah — in a satirical tone.

The mullah's a man — yet no will to serve, no zeal,

His rosary lost, no prayer stone, no kneeling feel.

His goblet lies empty, no wine left to pour.

As one of the greatest satirical poets of his time, Qasir often exposed the hypocrisy of mullahs in his satires. Although angry at the mullah's behavior, he tries to calm his friend Mæruh by mockingly ridiculing the cleric.

Further information about **Muhammadali beg Majruh Mughani** is also found in a manuscript known as "*The Divan of Mirza Bakhish Nadim*." Nadim is likewise one of the least-studied poets. His name appears in Salman Mumtaz's 1935 book "*Folk Poets*". Although Mumtaz provides no biographical information about him, he includes several of Nadim's poems in the collection.

Nadim's manuscript is currently preserved at the **Institute of Manuscripts named after M. Fuzuli** under the code **D-350/10327**. A note on the manuscript shows that it was previously catalogued under inventory number **8021**. The manuscript is not an autograph copy but a transcription made by **Agakerim Canibayli** from the original. On page 54, there is a note identifying Canibayli as the person who first wrote about Nadim, attempting to determine his birth and death dates and analyze his works:

"Teacher Agakerim Canibayli. Salyan, July 10, 1928." [8, 7]

On page 3 of the 250-page manuscript, Canibayli mentions Majruh Mughani:

"The poet introduced himself as both a native of Navahi and of Shirvan. In several parts of the manuscript and in his own divan, written in his own hand, he signed as 'Mirza Bakhish of Navahi'. His contemporaries and friends, the poets Molla Ibrahim (pen name Asi Salyani) and Muhammadali beg (pen name Mücrim Mughani), also referred to Mirza Bakhish as 'of Navahi'."

Canibayli ends his note about Majruh with a marginal comment marked "2":

"Muhammadali beg (Mücrim) Mughani. I could not definitively determine who this person was. From his correspondence with Nadim, it appears that he was originally from Shirvan and had been appointed by the Russians to a position in Mughan." [6, 3]

The manuscript contains poetic letters exchanged between the poets. The correspondence between Majruh Mughani and Mirza Bakhish Nadim clearly demonstrates that the two were close colleagues and friends.

As we can see, although Majruh Mughani was a well-known poet of his time, his written legacy has largely remained unstudied. The language, poetic structure, and content of his "*Divan*" show that Majruh was an artist who combined both **romantic and realistic elements** in his style. His poetic world reflects the influence of classical masters such as **Fuzuli, Khatai, and Vagif**, while also bearing traces of the **enlightenment and social thought of the 19th century**.

In his works, themes such as the **human inner world, the pursuit of moral perfection, justice, love, and humility** form the main motifs. Although his biography has not been fully reconstructed, his creative period is generally attributed to the **early 19th century**. Based on linguistic and stylistic features, it can be said that Majruh successfully united the **classical Arabic-Persian poetic tradition** with the **living style of Azerbaijani folk poetry**.

Today, the study of Majruh Mughani's work is not only the restoration of an individual poet's legacy but also an important step toward forming a **complete picture of 19th-century Azerbaijani literary life**.

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